

Polarographic Behaviour of Isopropyl Mercaptan (Propane-2-Thiol)

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The polarographic behaviour of isopropyl mercaptan [(CH₃)₂CH.SH] has been studied in presence of 10% ethanol and 0.1 M KNO₃ in the pH range (1.29-11.86) at the d.m.e. The electrode process is reversible in acidic media, irreversible in alkaline media and the plateau current is diffusion controlled in both. The half-wave potentials of the waves shift towards more negative values with increase in pH and the dissociation constant of sulphhydryl group is found to be 10.25. The maximum number of moles adsorbed per unit area is 8.0 × 10⁻¹⁰ moles/cm² i.e. 4.8 × 10¹⁴ molecules/cm², which corresponds to an area of 20.77 Å² per adsorbed molecule at h_{H₂O} = 51.5 cm. The adsorption coefficient and molar adsorption energy have been calculated as 13.57 × 10⁴ and 21.36 K. Cal/mole, respectively.

SAXENA and co-workers investigated the electrochemical behaviour of several mercapto compounds and their metal complexes¹⁻⁵, which have found important application in biological, pharmaceutical and chemical fields. The present communication reports the polarographic behaviour of isopropyl mercaptan in different buffers viz., Britton-Robinson, Clark and Lubs, Michaelis Borate, NH₃-NH₄Cl, CH₃COOH-CH₃COONa; solvents viz., acetonitrile, methanol, ethanol, *n*-butanol, isopropanol; supporting electrolytes, viz., KNO₃, NaClO₄, Li₂SO₄, KCl, (CH₃)₄NBr and (C₂H₅)₄NBr. The literature is, however, silent on these investigations.

Experimental

Isopropyl mercaptan (referred to herein as ISH) and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR (BDH) quality. As solutions of thiols oxidise in air forming disulphides, these should be kept out of contact with air. Hence, freshly prepared solutions of ISH in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air-oxidation. A manual polarograph with scalamp galvanometer and S.C.E. as reference electrode was used for recording the

of 0.1 M KNO₃ (pH 4.5) at -0.2 V vs S.C.E. with h_{eff} value 49.85 cm, m = 1.687 mg/sec, t = 4.85 sec, m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 1.844 mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}. Polarograms were recorded in an inert media of nitrogen at 20 ± 0.1°.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH (Fig. 1)

Polarograms for 1.0 mM ISH in presence of 10% ethanol and 0.1 M KNO₃ were recorded at different pH-values using Clark and Lubs buffers. An anodic

Fig. 1. Anodic wave of isopropyl mercaptan at different pH values.

wave associated with a small pre-wave at more negative potential was obtained at all pH values (1.29-10.50). From the values of slopes of $\log \left(\frac{i_d - i}{i} \right)$

vs. E_{de} , it was observed that the electrode reaction was reversible in acidic media and irreversible in alkaline media. At pH > 10.50 the pre-wave almost disappeared. The values of $E_{1/2}$ shift towards more negative potential with increase in pH. The point of intersection of the plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH corresponds to the dissociation constant (pK) of the sulphhydryl

TABLE I. EFFECT OF SUPPORTING ELECTROLYTE

Supporting electrolyte	$i_{d,c}$	I	$-E_{1/2}$	Slope
KNO ₃	3.40	1.844	0.1828	0.0571
NaClO ₄	3.43	1.861	0.1846	0.0600
KCl	3.45	1.871	0.1825	0.0571
Li ₂ SO ₄	3.58	1.942	0.1878	0.0540
(C ₂ H ₅) ₄ NBr	3.90	2.115	0.1886	0.0630
(OH ₃) ₄ NBr	3.93	2.130	0.1890	0.0632

polarograms. The capillary had the following characteristics in aqueous-10% ethanol, in presence

group⁶ under experimental conditions and is found to be 10.25 (Table 2).

 TABLE 2. $E_{1/2}$ vs pH

pH	$-E_{1/2}$	pH	$-E_{1/2}$
1.29	0.0545	9.80	0.4330
2.44	0.1000	10.50	0.4950
3.15	0.1375	11.36	0.5583
4.30	0.1925	11.55	0.5670
5.60	0.2400	11.86	0.5950
6.65	0.3000		

Polarograms of 1.0 mM ISH were recorded in different buffers and it was observed that the nature of the wave was not affected by the constituents of buffers.

Effects of solvents: The polarograms of 2.4 mM ISH at pH 4.50 in 0.1 M KNO₃ using different solvents were recorded which show a well defined reversible anodic wave with a very small pre-wave. I (diffusion current constant) varies in the following order:

Acetonitrile > methanol > ethanol > Isopropanol > n-Butanol.

This may be due to variation in viscosity of solution at 20° in the following order:

Acetonitrile < methanol < ethanol < Isopropanol < n-butanol
 (0.365 cp) (0.597 cp) (1.200 cp) (2.120 cp)
 (2.948 cp)

Effect of ISH concentration, Hg-pressure and temperature (Fig. 2)

i_d changes linearly with ISH concentration and the mean values of i_d/c and I were found to be 3.41

Fig. 2. Effect of varying [ISH], temperature and Hg-pressure.

Curves: (a) i_p vs. h_{eff} . (b) i_d vs. h_{eff} .
 (c) i_d vs. temp. (d) i_p vs. temp.
 (e) i_d vs. Conc. (f) i_p vs. Conc.

and 1.848, respectively. For 1.0 mM ISH I_d/h_{eff} (0.432 μ_A/cm^2) temperature-coefficient (1.374%) of i_d and (0.339%) of i_p (limiting adsorption current) were constant within experimental error, indicating diffusion controlled nature of the wave. The difference in $E_{1/2}$ of the main wave and that of pre-wave decreases with increase in temperature. This may be due to decrease in the energy of adsorption with increase in temperature.

Effect of different supporting electrolytes

Polarograms of 1.0 mM ISH at pH 4.5 in presence of 0.1 M different supporting electrolytes, produce a well defined reversible anodic wave with a small pre-wave. The nature of the wave remains unchanged and the diffusion current constant has been found to increase in the following order:

$(CH_3)_4NBr > (C_2H_5)_4NBr > Li_2SO_4 > KCl > NaClO_4 > KNO_3$

The values of I, $E_{1/2}$ and slope have been summarised in Table 1.

Controlled potential electrolysis and effect of HgCl₂

A solution of 1.0 mM ISH with 0.1 M KNO₃ in 10% ethanol at pH 4.5 was electrolysed in oxygen free nitrogen atmosphere for 6½ hrs at 0.04 V, $h_{Hg} = 5$ 1.5 cm. The electrolysed solution polarographed under identical conditions, exhibited an anodic wave with a decreased wave height than the unelectrolysed solution. The absence of composite wave confirmed that reaction product is an insoluble mercury complex. $E_{1/2}$ of the anodic wave before and after electrolysis was found to be the same within experimental error and indicates reversible nature of the anodic wave.⁷

[Fig. 3(B)] solutions containing ISH and HgCl₂ at pH 4.5 in proportions 1:0, 1:0.25 and 1:0.50 were prepared. The insoluble mercury-complex; was removed by filtration and filtrate then polarographed under identical conditions. With increase in amounts of HgCl₂, an anodic wave having proportionally decreased wave height was obtained, which disappeared completely when ISH and HgCl₂ were in the ratio (1:0.50), indicating the formation of (2:1) complex of ISH with Hg(II).

Mechanism of electrode reaction

The electro-oxidation of ISH may not involve the formation of disulphide $\begin{pmatrix} R-S \\ | \\ R-S \end{pmatrix}$ because the plots of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log \left(\frac{i_d - i}{i} \right)^2$ did not yield a straight line with a slope $\left(\frac{0.059}{2} \right)$ V, but yielded a straight line with a slope (0.059) V, corresponding to one electron transfer process.

Furthermore, the $E_{1/2}$ values were found to be independent of [ISH] which is characteristic of equation (1).

If the reaction is reversible, the mercury in the mercuric-ISH complex, should be reversibly reducible at the d.m.e., but the preceding experiments pertaining to the controlled potential analysis and the effect of added $HgCl_2$ show that the final product of the electrode reaction is an insoluble compound of Hg.

Thus, it may be concluded that ISH is not oxidised to disulphide but depolarizes the Hg with the formation of unstable mercurous mercaptide which rapidly changes into the more stable mercuric complex and mercury.

Adsorption pre-wave (Fig. 3A)

A steep depression in the $E-t$ curves was obtained for 1.0 mM ISH containing 0.1 M KNO_3 at pH 4.5

Fig. 3. (A) Electrocapillary curve at pH 4.50.
 (a) Aqueous—10% ethanol+0.1 M KNO_3 .
 (b) Aqueous—10% ethanol+0.1 M KNO_3 +1mM ISH.
 (B) Polarograms. (1) 1.0 mM ISH, (2) 1.0 mM ISH +0.25 mM $HgCl_2$, (3) 1.0 mM ISH+0.50 mM $HgCl_2$.

in the potential range where the pre-wave appeared, showing strong adsorption of electrolysis product at d.m.e.⁸. The maximum number of moles adsorbed per unit area is 8.0×10^{-10} moles/cm² i.e., 4.8×10^{14} molecules/cm² which corresponds to an area of 20.77 Å² per adsorbed molecule at a height of 51.5 cm. The adsorption coefficient and molar adsorption energy have been calculated as 13.57×10^4 and 21.36 Kcal/mole, respectively.

Kinetic parameters: In higher alkaline media pH > 10.50 a well defined irreversible anodic wave is obtained. Hence Koutecky's⁹ theoretical treatment as modified by Meites and Israel¹⁰ was used for evaluating kinetic parameters. The values of the formal rate constant $K^{\circ}_{b,h}$ and transfer coefficient (α) were found to be 4.80×10^{-4} cm/sec and 0.375, respectively in 10% ethanolic media at pH 11.10 and temperature $(34^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ})$.¹¹

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